

An Innovative Look at the Issue of Climate Change

Amazon Book Review Series of “*Better Economics for the Earth: A Lesson from Quantum and Information Theories*”

Brian Conklin

January 8, 2025

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Since the very beginning of the climate movement, there has been a question at the forefront of the activists and decision makers at the forefront of the movement, why don't more people care? And how do we heighten the urgency society feels to take action?

The authors examine the question through the lens of economics, particularly through a reimagined economics that rejects the traditional "growth above all" models and thinking as outdated. They want us to incorporate different ways to think about happiness and societal health themselves. They posit an interesting theory of quantum economics, that incorporates uncertainty. They also have interesting ideas of how to make eco-friendly ideas more accessible to the greater public.

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★★★★☆ Innovative look at the issue of climate change

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Where it ultimately falls short is where too many climate change and eco-activism does: Who actually will oversee all these massive societal changes that will change the fundamental ways people live? Elected officials? They would be too sensitive to causing their constituents pain that would cost them votes. Inevitably, we come to the unelected bureaucrat, imbued with monstrous power, willing and able to stomp all over the liberty of the individual, all in the name of "the Earth". It's a frightening vision, one most people reject. I'd be interested to know if they have an answer.

Screenshot. Review of “*Better Economics for the Earth*” by Conklin [1]. Reviewed in the United States on January 8, 2025.

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(* Note: This paper reprints Conklin's review [1] appearing on the Amazon page of the title [2].

References

[1] Conklin, B. (2025, Jan. 8). Innovative look at the issue of climate change. <https://www.amazon.com/gp/customer-reviews/R3GJYEWCR403S0/>

[2] Vuong, Q. H. & Nguyen, M. H. (2024). *Better Economics for the Earth: A Lesson from Quantum and Information Theories*. <https://www.amazon.com/dp/B0D98L5K44>